

Scalable full-cycle marine litter remediation in the Mediterranean: Robotic and participatory solutions

SeaClear2.0

<https://www.seaclear2.eu>

D1.3

Data Management Plan

WP1 – Management & coordination of consortium & associated regions

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Dissemination level: PU

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Deliverable description	The developed Data Management Plan (DMP) describes how the technical data and knowledge that is collected, processed, or created within SeaClear2.0 will be handled, stored, and made accessible. The DMP will be updated yearly.

¹ R = Document, report, DEM = Demonstrator, OTHER = Software, technical diagram, etc., DMP = Data Management Plan

² PU = Public, C-UE/EU-C = EU Confidential under Decision 2015/444, SEN = Sensitive

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Definitions

- **Beneficiary:** A legal entity that is signatory of the EC Grant Agreement no. 101093822.
- **Consortium:** The SeaClear2.0 Consortium, comprising the list of beneficiaries below.
- **Consortium Agreement:** Agreement concluded amongst the SeaClear2.0 beneficiaries for the implementation of the Grant Agreement.
- **Grant Agreement:** The agreement signed between the beneficiaries and the EC for the undertaking of the SeaClear2.0 project (Grant Agreement no. 101093822).

Beneficiaries of the SeaClear2.0 Consortium are referred to herein according to the following abbreviations:

- **TU Delft:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT
- **DUNEA:** REGIONALNA AGENCIJA DUNEA
- **Fraunhofer:** FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FOERDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV
- **HPA:** HAMBURG PORT AUTHORITY
- **ISOTECH:** ISOTECH LTD
- **MDanchor:** M. DANCHOR LTD
- **Subsea Tech:** SUBSEA TECH SAS
- **TECNOSUB:** TÉCNICAS Y OBRAS SUBACUÁTICAS, SLU
- **TUM:** TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN
- **UNIDU:** SVEUCILISTE U DUBROVNIKU
- **UTC:** UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA CLUJ-NAPOCA
- **VEO:** VEOLIA PROPRETE
- **VLPF:** VENICE LAGOON PLASTIC FREE

Abbreviations

- **EC:** European Commission
- **GA:** Grant Agreement
- **WP:** Work Package
- **DPM:** Data Management Plane
- **IMU:** Inertial Measurement Unit
- **DVL:** Doppler Velocity Log
- **Wi-Fi:** Wireless Fidelity
- **AI:** Artificial Intelligence
- **GPS:** Global Positioning System
- **DOI:** Digital Object Identifier
- **PAKE:** Password Authenticated Key Exchange
- **EULA:** End-User-Licence-Agreement
- **UUV:** Unmanned Underwater Vehicle
- **SSH:** Social Sciences and Humanities

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Executive summary

This data management plan is developed to ensure that project data will be managed in a way that maximizes its value, facilitates its sharing and reuse, and complies with relevant policies, regulations, and standards. The data management plan provides clear guidelines to effectively organize, document, store, and share research results in compliance with components of quality, transparency, and reusability. The use of reliable techniques for data collection, processing, analysis, and preservation supports these guidelines.

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1. Data Summary

SeaClear2.0 will use various datasets to improve the capabilities of the robotic system, analyse and monitor environmental conditions and aggregate social science and policy information. Several datasets were already identified (TrashCan¹ and SeaClear1.0 datasets) towards improving sensors, litter detection techniques, control, and mapping software. Information on environmental conditions the system has not encountered, beach litter, societal impacts and policies affecting marine litter will be aggregated and / or created for each demo site within the course of the project.

Based on that, the DMP will be regularly updated, and the datasets will be described and evaluated for publishing under an open access policy without compromising the privacy and security of the data subjects or exploitation opportunities. The following list illustrates the developed SeaClear datasets that are expected to be re-used in the work packages of SeaClear2.0:

Existing SeaClear datasets			
No.	Dataset Name	Owner	Description
1	DS-1-HPA-Video/Photo Footage-1	HPA	Photo and video images of the port of Hamburg for dissemination and exploitation purposes as well as technical developments. Footage may include (aerial) images of the port, test locations and debris findings.
2	DS-2-HPA-Technical Infrastructure-1	HPA	Specific data for the test areas at Hamburg port including information on the WIFI network, access points, bandwidth, and speed to enable data flows, processing and refining within the SeaClear systems.
3	DS-3-HPA-Hydrographic maps -1	HPA	The data set supplies specified Geo information on a designated test area in terms of bathymetry. It also indicates maritime navigation marks and (estimated) tidal movements.
4	DS-0-Subsea Tech-Exampleset-1	SST	The dataset is composed essentially of equipment operation description, mechanical 3D design and manufacturing plans, software architecture and code, electrotechnics and electronics design.
5	DS-0-UTC-MapSample-1	UTC	This dataset will mostly be useful for research and simulations involving motion planning to collect the litter
6	DS 001 TUM UUVMotion 01	TUM	The dataset includes a collection of raw measurements of an Unmanned Underwater vehicle moving in an underwater environment obtained from onboard sensors such as IMU, DVL, and video during the robot's motion. It will be valuable for benchmarking sensor-fusion, identification, and data-driven control algorithms.
7	DS-1-UNIDU-Multimediaset-1	UNIDU	This dataset includes photos and videos of test sites in Dubrovnik for dissemination and exploitation purposes and technical developments. Footage includes aerial and underwater images of test locations and other nearby locations and debris found.
8	DS-1-UNIDU-Soft-architecture-1	UNIDU	Includes the openly available software architecture, but the code will remain closed due to exploitation potential.

¹ <https://doi.org/10.13020/g1gx-y834>

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The following table lists new foreseeable datasets and research results, which will be created/updated over the project's course.

Planned SeaClear2.0 datasets					
Name	Data collected / generated	Re-used data	Data sharing platform	Size of new data	Access Type
Labelled litter dataset	Videos, images, sonar images, magnetic data recordings	Existing labelled camera and sonar images	Zenodo	Order of 4TB	Open access
Litter mapped on surface and underwater over the system's region of operation	Bathymetry, surface and seabottom litter locations	Possibly existing bathymetry	Zenodo	Order of 100MB	Open access
Robot sensor and control data	Sensor data with estimated pose	Integration of existing UUV motion dataset	MediaTUM repository	Order of 1GB	Open access
Larger-scale litter map	Images, litter descriptions or type, GPS coordinates, timestamps	Data obtained from public reporting	Zenodo Project website	Scales with number of submissions MBs/report	Open access
Beach marine litter data	Images, amounts and types of collected beach marine litter	-	Zenodo	Order of GBs	Open access
Social science analysis perception of societal actors	Questionnaires, event evaluations	Literature past projects conducted by partners	Zenodo (no personal data shared)	Order of 10GB	Open access
Aggregation of policies affecting seabed marine litter	Documents, structural classification	Literature on marine litter policies	Zenodo	Order of GBs	Open access

The foreseeable datasets are related to project work packages as follow:

- **Labelled litter dataset:** Creating a database of marine litter by gathering information from marine scientific reports and field studies, categorizing waste fractions by size, material, weight, solidity, location (water surface, column, floor, beach) in the designated demonstration areas. Photo and video recording will contribute to further AI training in T2.4.
- **Litter mapping:** The detected litter will be placed on a map of the seafloor. A 2D map for surface litter, and a 3D map for water-column litter will be created in T4.5. Active exploration will be used via blending seafloor-mapping with litter-detection objectives.
- **Robot sensor and control data:** From sensors such as inertial measurement units, Doppler velocity loggers, GPS, and ultra-short baseline, new datasets will be created (T4.3) in relevant

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environments, to customize deep-learning frameworks, and then to train them for litter detection and segmentation.

- **Larger-scale litter map:** Detailed litter maps will be obtained, which then can be used to monitor litter quantities and fractions in the deployment areas, and to direct cleaning actions. The public-engagement strategy (T6.3) further provides a source of litter monitoring.
- **Beach marine litter data:** Litter maps will be created to monitor beach marine litter and to make it a significantly clean and healthy environment. These maps will also increase public awareness towards litter reduction T6.3.
- **Social science analysis perception of societal actors:** Several activities have been planned in the project, particularly in WP6 and WP8. The input of SSH processes in the project will be instrumental in the work related to decision-making workshops and the Policy Roundtable.
- **Aggregation of policies affecting seabed marine litter:** Relevant information will be gathered on the barriers and opportunities that exist for the prevention and minimization of marine litter through an analysis of the relevant policies. This analysis will result in the key factors and policy recommendations to consider for the uptake of our innovations (T6.5).

2. FAIR data

SeaClear2.0 will respect the principles of FAIR data management, that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The Zenodo will be the main dataset repository that stores the data in a permanent and sustainable manner. It also supports the Open Science. This repository will ensure that datasets are findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable for future research. In the same context, the FAIR data principles are secured.

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

To make the data findable, a persistent Identifier (DOI) will be assigned to each dataset to ensure that data is consistently localized. It is also citable and readable by humans and machines as well. A license is provided to guarantee the openness and reusability of our data. The embargo period access privilege can be configured as well as granting license for data.

In addition, descriptive keywords will be added to increase data visibility. Metadata such as title, authors, data description, data format, and other relevant contextual information will also be combined with the datasets. Using standardized vocabularies and taxonomies to describe datasets will promote their availability. The standardized metadata schemas will contribute to data FAIR as well.

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Some datasets may be stored in another repository system when extra security is needed, such as for data covered by the IP rights of partners. Links to all datasets will be listed on the project website. Data that can be made open access will be submitted to the repository within six months after the approval of the deliverable they have contributed to.

2.2 Making data accessible

Datasets will be openly accessible after the publication of a scientific paper or filing of a patent directly resulting from the dataset. Before making them public, all data will be screened by the exploitation chair for appropriateness. This will allow researchers, policymakers, and the public to access and use the data freely.

Any data that may result in identifying individuals or groups of individuals will not be made publicly available. Furthermore, any data that may compromise exploitation opportunities by the consortium members will be set aside from open access.

The datasets will use standards and common data formats that are accessible among different platforms and software. Standard video and image tools could be used to explore the open access datasets.

Zenodo repository is a trusted repository, meaning it complies with requirements related to organisational governance, data management and technical infrastructure. It offers three access levels for the datasets:

- **Open Access:** There are no restrictions on access to the data. Anyone can view and download a copy where Open access is the default setting by which all datasets will be directly accessible to others free of charge. The data will be available via Open Access and stored for 15 years at least. Each file copy has two replicas located on different disk servers.
- **Embargoed Access:** In some cases, it may be needed to delay the publication of datasets until the scientific papers are published.
- **Restricted Access:** If the data contains sensitive information that cannot be removed without the losing value, then Restricted Access is the option. The Reason and the conditions must be provided before selecting the restricted access type. Any user can request access to the datasets. The user's email address, name and reason must be prefilled. Users requesting access will be asked to justify how they fulfil the conditions. Based on the justification, the data owner

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decides who to grant/deny access. Once the access to data is granted, the user can download it.

2.3 Making data Interoperable

Making data interoperable involves ensuring that data can be shared or accessed by external researchers across different systems and applications to boost mutual research and paves the road toward new horizons. Following actions can make the project data more interoperable:

- Using of standardize and common data formats to ensure that the data can be easily understood and used without special tools, software, or any other legal restrictions.
- The format should be readable without technical constraints such as encryption or digital rights.
- Applied multimedia formats that should compress lossless.
- Providing documentation about the dataset and used software can help other researchers to understand its content and context.
- Ensure that the data is well-organized and secure. This can help to ensure that the data is easily shared and used by others.

2.4 Increase data Re-use

Before making it public, all datasets will be screened by the exploitation chair for potential exploitation opportunities and appropriateness and will be displayed on the project website. The documentation will describe the datasets (data paper) and download links of the datasets. This document will explain the structure, content, data collection methodology, and any data transformations or pre-processing that have been performed. It also will help users understand the data and facilitate its proper interpretation as well as possibilities for data re-use. The datasets will be designed to allow easy re-use with commonly available tools and software libraries. Commercial video and image players could be used to view the collected dataset. We envisage making the data available for re-use for a duration of a minimum of 15 years.

3. Allocation of resources

The primary data archive (Zenodo) operates free of charge, up to 50GB of data per record. Higher quotas can be requested and granted on a case-by-case basis. Moreover, since the internal communication is key to an efficient and smooth execution of the project, the project coordinator will

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set up a network drive to provide a common workspace for saving and sharing all working documents, minutes, and reports within the SeaClear2.0 consortium. This network drive is provided free of charge to all project partners.

Furthermore, network attached storage will be allocated as a backup for storing the data archives at the TUM premise for all datasets archived through Zenodo. It will also store all materials shared between the consortium partners such as deliverables, meeting minutes, and presentations. The one-time small cost for the storage will be covered by the project during the project, and the host (TUM) will cover the maintenance cost after the project. The data will be kept available at least 10 years after the completion of the project.

For the datasets that will not be centralised at Zenodo, the data owner will be responsible for local storage and may also incur small one-time cost covered by the project.

4. Data security

The foreseen datasets to be collected through SeaClear2.0 project are of high value and may contain sensitive personal data or proprietary information from consortium partners. Special care should be taken to prevent such a data leak or become hacked. During the project period, partners' data, such as research results, reports, meeting minutes, presentations, etc., will be stored on local servers maintained and automatically backed up by the partners responsible for the activities. A holistic security approach will be followed to protect the pillars of information security (confidentiality, integrity, availability). The performed security approach will consist of a methodical assessment of security risks followed by their impact analysis. The performed analysis includes personal information, data processed by the proposed system, their flows, and any associated risk with their processing. Security measures also will include the implementation of Password Authenticated Key Exchange (PAKE) protocols and protection against bots such as captcha technologies. Furthermore, we will apply monitored and controlled procedures related to data collection, integrity, and protection. The data protection and privacy of personal information will include protective measures against infiltration as physical protection of core parts of the systems and access control measures.

5. Ethics

SeaClear2.0 activities will involve human participants in various human activities during experiments and demonstrations (i.e., human-in-the-loop). Therefore, in some cases, personal data may be collected. Such data will be protected under the EU's Data Protection laws, where the main legislation is Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the

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protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing directive 95/46/EC, also known as the ‘General Data Protection Regulation’ (GDPR), which entered into force on 25 May 2018. Further information on personal data collection and handling approached in the SeaClear2.0 project Deliverable (D1.4: *Ethics Procedures and Documents*). When dealing with personal data (e.g., questionnaires), informed consent will be required from participants before any data collection to describe information for data sharing and long-term preservation.

6. Deposit license agreement

To guarantee the proper function of the Data management of SeaClear2.0 project, a License agreement was prepared for the cases where the owner of a dataset wishes to upload it on the Data management portal (e.g., Zenodo) and distribute it directly in this way to the public. The following parties are involved in this Licence agreement:

- The organisation or person authorised to transfer and deposit the digital data, hereafter referred to as the Depositor.
- The organisation that is authorized to archive and manage the digital data, hereafter referred to as the Repository.

6.1 Licence

The Depositor grants the Repository a non-exclusive license for digital data files, hereafter referred to as ‘dataset/document’. The Repository is authorized to include the dataset/document in its data archive. The Repository shall transfer the content of the dataset/document to an available carrier, through any method and in any form. The Repository is authorized to make the dataset/document (or substantial parts thereof) available to third parties by means of online transmission. In addition, the Repository has the right, on the instruction of third parties or otherwise, to make a copy of the dataset/document or to grant third parties’ permission to download a copy.

6.2 The Depositor

- The Depositor declares that he is a holder of rights to the dataset/document, or the only holder of rights to the dataset/document, under the Databases act and where relevant, the Copyright actor otherwise, and/or is entitled to act in the present matter with the permission of other parties that hold rights.

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- By depositing a dataset/document, the Depositor does not transfer ownership. The Depositor retains the right to deposit the dataset/document elsewhere in its present or future version(s). The Depositor retains all moral rights in the dataset/document including the right to be acknowledged as creator.
- The Depositor indemnifies the Repository against all claims made by other parties against the Repository with regard to the dataset/document, the transfer of the dataset/document, and the form and/or content of the dataset/document.

6.3 Dataset/document

- The dataset/document to which the license relates consists of all the databases, documentation and other data files and documents that form part of this dataset/document, which have been transferred by the Depositor.
- The Depositor declares that the dataset/document corresponds to the specification provided.
- The Depositor declares that the dataset/document contains no data or other elements that are contrary to European law.
- The Depositor will supply the dataset/document by means of a method and medium deemed acceptable by the Repository.

6.4 Repository

- The Repository shall ensure, to the best of its ability and resources, that the deposited dataset/document is archived in a sustainable manner and remains legible and accessible.
- The Repository shall, as far as possible, preserve the dataset/document unchanged in its original software format, taking account of current technology and the costs of implementation. The Repository has the right to modify the format and/or functionality of the dataset/document if this is necessary in order to facilitate the digital sustainability, distribution, or re-use of the dataset/document.

6.5 Removal of dataset/documents

If sufficient weighty grounds exist, the Repository has the right to remove the dataset/document from the archive wholly or in part, or to restrict or prevent access to the dataset/document on a temporary or permanent basis. The Repository shall inform the Depositor in such cases.

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6.6 Availability to third parties

- The Repository shall make the dataset/document available to third parties in accordance with the access conditions agreed with the Depositor: "Open Access".
- The Repository shall make the dataset/document available only to third parties who have agreed to comply with the General conditions of use.
- Notwithstanding the above, the Repository can make the dataset/document (or substantial parts thereof) available to third parties if:
 - o the Repository is required to do so by legislation or regulations, a court decision, or by a regulatory or other institution,
 - o this is necessary for the preservation of the dataset/document and/or the data archive,
 - o (to a similar institution) the Repository ceases to exist and/or its activities in the field of data archiving are terminated.
- The Repository shall publish the metadata and make them freely available, on the basis of the documentation that the Depositor provides with the dataset/document. The term metadata refers to the information that describes the digital files.
- The general information about the research and the metadata relating to the dataset/document shall be included in the Repository's databases and publications that are freely accessible to all persons.

6.7 Provisions relating to use by third parties

- The Repository shall require third parties to whom the dataset/document (or substantial parts thereof) is made available to include in the research results a clear reference to the dataset/document from which data have been used. The reference must comply with the General conditions of use.
- The Repository shall require parties to which a dataset/document is made available to grant a non-exclusive license for the dataset/document(s) they create using the dataset/document that has been made available.

6.8 Liability

- The Repository accepts no liability in the event that all or part of a dataset/document is lost.

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- The Repository accepts no liability for any damage or losses resulting from acts or omissions by third parties to whom the Repository has made the dataset/document available.
- The Repository accepts no responsibility for mistakes, omissions, or legal infringements within the deposited dataset/document.

6.9 Term and termination of the Agreement

- This Agreement shall come into effect on the date on which the Repository receives the dataset/document (hereafter the deposit date) and shall remain valid for an indefinite period. If the repository decides not to include the dataset/document in its data archive, this Agreement is cancelled. The Repository notifies the Depositor of publication or non-inclusion of the dataset/document in its data archive. Cancellation of this Agreement is subject to a period of notice of six months, and notice shall be given in writing. It is possible to change the agreed access category at any time during the term of the Agreement.
- Notwithstanding point (a), this Agreement shall end when the dataset/document is removed from the data archive in accordance with this Agreement.
- If the Repository ceases to exist or terminates its data-archiving activities, the Repository shall attempt to transfer the data files to a similar organization that will continue the Agreement with the Depositor under similar conditions if possible.

6.10 Jurisdiction

The SeaClear2.0 Data Management Platform is entitled, but not obliged, to act independently against violations of the Copyright Act and/or any other intellectual property right of the holder(s) of rights to the dataset/document and/or the data from the dataset/document.

6.11 Applicable law

Dutch law is applicable to this agreement.